

ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION FOR GLOBAL ECONOMIC PROGRESS: NIGERIAN PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Entrepreneurship education has emerged as a critical driver of global progress, equipping individuals with the skills, mindset, and knowledge necessary to navigate the complexities of the modern business landscape. This paper examines the multifaceted impact of entrepreneurship education on economic growth, innovation, and societal development in Nigeria. The paper identified challenges of entrepreneurship which include insufficient educational resources, insufficient resources and tools for instruction and learning, and a lack of qualified instructors to teach entrepreneurship at different educational institutions. The paper stated that the purpose of entrepreneurship education includes fostering self-employment, creativity and innovation. The paper concluded that the Federal Government of Nigeria should endeavor to provide a guide to the development and implementation of effective entrepreneurship education policies. These include enhancing funding, promoting inclusivity, supporting curriculum innovation, and fostering partnerships. By addressing these challenges and embracing innovative approaches, entrepreneurship education can continue to evolve and contribute significantly to global economic growth, innovation, and sustainable development.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education, Economic Growth, Innovation, Challenges, Prospects, Policy Implications.

Introduction

Although education has long been promoted as one of the most obvious routes out of poverty, the growing proportion of unemployed university graduates calls into question this claim. Unemployment could therefore be seen as a consequence of a non-functional education system. Including entrepreneurial education in the curriculum is a method to ensure that education helps address both domestic and global unemployment (Obeta, Uchejeso, and Philemon, 2020). According to Olubamise,

et al, in Ubogu (2022), Nigeria is one of the few countries in the world endowed with a thriving agricultural foundation, an enterprising populace, and an abundance of mineral resources. Because of its size and population density, it is ideally situated to serve as the center of economic activity in Africa. The chance to leverage the private sector—entrepreneurs—to propel economic growth and close the wealth gap is provided by entrepreneurship education. According to Beetseh and Ahima (2012), entrepreneurship is frequently employed to

foster enterprising behavior and instill a self-reliant mindset through the use of suitable learning procedures.

The creation or extraction of economic value is known as entrepreneurship. According to this definition, entrepreneurship is defined as a state of transformation that typically involves a higher level of risk than is typical when launching a business and may involve values beyond just financial ones. A person who starts and/or invests in one or more enterprises, taking on the majority of the risks and reaping the majority of the gains, is referred to as an entrepreneur. Entrepreneurship is the process of starting a business. It is a popular perception that an entrepreneur is an innovator, a supplier of fresh concepts, products, services, and business practices (Wikipedia, 2022).

A broad definition of entrepreneurship was given by French economist Jean-Baptiste Say in the early 19th century. He stated that it is the transfer of financial resources from a region of lower production and more yield to one of higher productivity and greater yield. Entrepreneurs transform or produce something new. They also alter or transform values. All sizes of firms are eligible to participate in entrepreneurship initiatives.

Four requirements must be met to have the chance to start a business. For there to be a profit, there must first be circumstances or chances to recombine resources. Second, individual variations are necessary for entrepreneurship, such as having preferred access to particular people or having the capacity to discern information about opportunities. Third, it's imperative to take risks. Fourth, organizing people and resources is a necessary step in the entrepreneurial process. An entrepreneur invests his time, effort, and money in making valuable things for other people. He receives financial compensation for his efforts, which benefits the

entrepreneur as well as the recipient of the value produced (Wikipedia, 2022).

Entrepreneurship Education

According to Salami (2011), as referenced in Adamu (2015), as nearly all industrialized nations have embraced entrepreneurship education, it is critical to foster the culture and spirit of entrepreneurship education in developing nations as well. Education in entrepreneurship is the kind that molds people's perspectives and gives them the abilities and information needed to create an entrepreneurial culture.

Since education is widely recognized as a measure of development, it is crucial to incorporate entrepreneurial education into current curricula to improve competitive advantage. Since then, the reciprocal linkages between education and development have been established. According to Adamu, [2015] entrepreneurship education is the organized, formal delivery of entrepreneurship competencies, which are the ideas, abilities, and state of mind that people employ when launching and growing their growth-oriented businesses. The purpose of entrepreneurship education is to foster self-employment, creativity, and innovation by helping students acquire the qualities and abilities that underpin an entrepreneurial attitude and way of acting.

- Technical expertise and training: The information specialist is becoming increasingly important in today's digital information landscape due to the internet's deluge of information. A successful career as an information professional, such as a librarian, requires computer proficiency.
- Organizational and assessment skills: One of the main competencies of the reference material is the capacity to multitask and juggle multiple tasks. Information specialists are frequently requested to carry out duties such as

helping users find information, ordering or discarding library books, and creating presentations about the library for audiences such as the community or a board of directors. A librarian or other information specialist would struggle to keep up with the volume and variety of work without strong organizational abilities. Working one-on-one with a user to find an answer to a specific topic develops organizational and assessment abilities in addition to the information specialist's overall capacity to multitask and organize.

- **Marketing and interpersonal skills:** Being able to interact with people who come to look for information is crucial for librarians and other information specialists. They ought to get along well with both their bosses and other co-workers, both nearby and far away. Regarding library users, a reference interview is essential to any fruitful communication between an information scientist or reference librarian and a user. A librarian or information scientist can learn what the user wants and in what format by conducting this conversation.
- **Managing finances:** Any successful librarian or information specialist needs to have constant conversations about finances. He/she needs to develop prudent money management skills. He can't be a wasteful person.
- **Taking risks:** This is a crucial ability that an entrepreneur in the information and library fields needs to master. He or she needs to learn how to take risks, manage them, and turn a profit when the time comes. It is hard for any entrepreneur to succeed if they are not willing to take risks.

Entrepreneurship Education for Economic Growth

A country's economic development depends on its level of education. Without

its citizens being educated, a country cannot achieve economic prosperity. According to Iwu and Nzeako (2012), entrepreneurship plays the following functions in a country's economic growth:

1. It encourages links between facilities and the economy: Without interacting with other businesses or groups for various purposes, no business can exist in isolation. In terms of production, distribution, and preservation, there appears to be a relationship between the different economic sectors. The local labor force, technical know-how, and services required to run and maintain facilities for continuous production are provided via entrepreneurship education.
2. It imparts knowledge on Mobilizing Rural Savings: One policy to assist in the mobilization of rural savings for economic purposes is the development of community banks, which is facilitated by entrepreneurship education. The savings contribute to an increase in rural areas' economic activity.
3. It teaches the utilization of local resources and raw materials, which has assisted in cleaning up local agricultural goods through the formation of small businesses that employ the products for local manufacture, hence reducing waste.
4. It facilitates the creation of job opportunities. As a result, small and medium-sized businesses create more jobs overall than the majority of large corporations. A lot of people rely on their businesses for work, and they could even hire helpers.
5. It helps to promote the growth of indigenous businesses. Therefore, the knowledge and abilities acquired in small businesses

- support large-firm operations and management.
6. It facilitates the transformation of conventional enterprises. Through entrepreneurship education, local and indigenous industries and technology can be developed. Through indigenous entrepreneurship education, nations like South Korea, Taiwan, Japan, Singapore, and others, saw significant improvements in their native and traditional sectors.
 7. **Increases Living Standards:** The ability of entrepreneurship to significantly raise the standard of life for people and communities through the establishment of industries, the creation of wealth, and the creation of new jobs plays a crucial role in economic development. In addition to creating jobs and sources of revenue on a broad scale, entrepreneurship can enhance people's quality of life by creating goods and services that are reasonably priced, secure, and bring value to their lives. Additionally, entrepreneurship creates new goods and services that eliminate the scarcity of necessities.
 8. **Financial Self-Sufficiency:** Both the nation and the entrepreneur will achieve financial independence through entrepreneurship. It encourages self-sufficiency and lessens the dependency of the country on imported goods and services. Exporting the produced goods and services to overseas markets can result in growth, independence, revenue inflow, and economic independence. Entrepreneurs also have total control over their financial destiny. They earn money and build wealth via their diligence and creativity, which enables them to attain financial security and economic independence.
 9. **Employment Generation:** One important factor in the generation of jobs is entrepreneurship. There are new job opportunities created by managing the operations of new enterprises and satisfying consumer expectations. In addition to fostering innovation and competition, entrepreneurship also stimulates investments and other entrepreneurs, resulting in the creation of new jobs across a variety of industries, including the manufacturing, construction, service, and technology sectors.
 10. **Increases per capita income and the gross national product:** By raising the Gross National Product (GNP) and Per Capita Income (PCI), entrepreneurship can significantly contribute to economic growth and prosperity. PCI determines the average income per person, whereas GNP assesses a nation's overall economic production. PCI may rise in response to an increase in GNP. By spawning new companies and sectors, entrepreneurship can boost the gross national product (GNP) and generate jobs, higher consumer spending, and more tax income.

Challenges of Entrepreneurship Education

1. **Insufficient Educational Resources:** Educational resources encompass any type of data that can be utilized for logging, archiving, sending, or obtaining data to facilitate teaching and learning. Adewole (2015), Ezike and Obodo (1991) state that instructional materials are the tools teachers use to educate in the classroom. According to Adekola (2010), one of the elements affecting functional education in

- Nigeria is instructional materials. Unfortunately, the teaching resources used in Nigerian entrepreneurial education programs are insufficient to reflect contemporary societal trends in skill acquisition. Even the teaching strategies used in Nigerian schools are inadequate for the practical component of entrepreneurial education, and there is a dearth of high-quality entrepreneurial textbooks.
2. Insufficient resources and tools for instruction and learning: The lack of proper resources and tools for the subject's instruction is one of the biggest issues facing Nigerian entrepreneurship education. The world of business and education is driven by technology, with information and communication technology (ICT) seeing the most significant developments. Regretfully, these facilities and equipment are lacking from our institutions; in fact, some of the items that are here at our school are outdated.
 3. Keeping Theory and Practice in Check: Another issue facing entrepreneurial education is finding the ideal mix between theoretical knowledge and real-world experience. Although practical learning is highly regarded, it needs to be supported by a strong theoretical framework that gives students access to fundamental business concepts and analytical abilities (Neck et al., 2018). It is still difficult for educators to create courses that successfully incorporate both components (Piperopoulos & Dimov, 2021).
 4. Insufficient motivation among the teaching and non-teaching information staff members, which impacts their productivity, retention, inventiveness, and initiative.
 5. The issues raised by globalization and information and communication technology (ICT) have an impact on library and information center staffing, facilities, curriculum, and methods.
 6. A lack of qualified instructors to teach entrepreneurship at different educational institutions.

Conclusion

An abundance of entrepreneurial knowledge aimed at complete economic emancipation for users should be utilized by entrepreneurship education centers instead of chasing shadow or job prospects where none exist. The federal and state governments of Nigeria have ordered the rapid implementation of entrepreneurship education in all of the nation's post-secondary schools to curb the wave of unrest among the country's youth, which is a result of unemployment. Before the federal government, certain state governments have revived and reintroduced entrepreneurial and vocational programs into their respective high school curricula, just as they did in the past (Babalola and Abifarin, n.d). Therefore, to support Nigeria's economic development, entrepreneurship education centers should be prepared to gather and distribute knowledge resources on entrepreneurship education to academics, teachers, and students.

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